

FIBRE-REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE OSTEOSYNTHESIS IMPLANTS WITH VARIABLE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES FOR BETTER TREATMENT OF BONE FRACTURES

J. Krebs¹, K. Friedrich¹, R. Heuwinkel², P. Rieger³, P. Kosack³

¹ *Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH, University of Kaiserslautern,
Erwin-Schroedinger-Str. 58, 67663 Kaiserslautern, Germany*

² *Department for Casualty Surgery, Klinikum der Universitätsstadt Kaiserslautern,
Friedrich-Engels-Str. 25, 67655 Kaiserslautern, Germany*

³ *Centre for Microelectronics, University of Kaiserslautern,
Erwin-Schroedinger-Str. 12, 67663 Kaiserslautern, Germany*

SUMMARY: A new thermoplastic composite femoral implant was designed and manufactured following the concept of semi-rigid fixation. By integrating a biodegradable polymer block into the body of the implant it was made sufficiently rigid to initially enable primary bony union but, with progressive degradation, to also enable interfragmentary movement, which promotes the proliferation of external callus and consequently a better consolidation of the fracture. In order to meet medical standards the parts of the implant were manufactured by injection moulding and near-net-shape forming. The degradation behaviour of Poly (L-lactide) was studied *in-vitro* under static and dynamic loading conditions. It was found that dynamic loading leads to mechanical degradation of the polymer long before hydrolytic degradation commences.

KEYWORDS: medical applications, osteosynthesis implants, semi-rigid fixation, resorbable polyesters, near-net-shape forming, ooly (l-lactide), CF/PEEK, biodegradation

INTRODUCTION

Historically, high performance alloys such as CoCrMo and Ti6Al4V along with ultra high molecular weight polyethylene, acrylic bone cement, and more recently, ceramics have been the materials of choice within the orthopaedic community [1]. These materials have proved their biocompatibility and mechanical properties necessary to stabilise fractured bones. With increasing understanding of the processes occurring during cortical healing of diaphyseal fractures, however, it has become obvious that both stainless steel and titanium alloy implants hold a significant drawback, that is, their comparatively high stiffness. According to recent studies, secondary bone healing, which is generally accompanied by the formation of external callus, can only take place when interfragmentary movement is enabled [2-7]. The purpose of callus, that ideally shapes around the fracture like a cuff, is to re-establish the structural integrity of the bone shortly after fracture has taken place. With progressive re-consolidation the callus cuff subsequently regresses until the bone's initial strength is fully restored. Employing metallic implants, such micro movements are strongly hampered, and therefore, in absence of external callus, union has to take place directly between the fractured bone ends. In

medical terms this curing process is described as primary or remodelling bony union. In this case, the re-consolidation process progresses extremely slow and consequently the implant cannot be removed safely for at least 18 months. Problems that may result from such a prolonged dependence are implant failure due to shortcomings in surgical technique, allergic reactions, and osteopenia. The latter encompasses all types of bone infections which mainly develop beneath very strong steel plates as a result of protection against stress which they confer. In view of these apparent drawbacks of metallic implants, advanced fibre-reinforced composites have become increasingly appealing as a new group of materials for orthopaedic bone fixation plates. Early laboratory studies on carbon fibre/polysulfone [8], carbon fibre/methylmethacrylate, carbon fibre/epoxy [9] and carbon/carbon implants in animals have demonstrated the potential advantage of composite over metallic implants. In addition, properties such as good biocompatibility, excellent fatigue properties, transparency to X-rays and, most importantly, the opportunity to individually tailor the elastic properties of the implant to that of the host bone positively add to the characteristic property profile of composite materials.

DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION

In the frame of an ongoing project at the University of Kaiserslautern in cooperation with the Clinic of Kaiserslautern, a new osteosynthesis implant was designed made from fibre reinforced thermoplastics. Following the concept of semi-rigid fixation it was aimed to tailor the mechanical properties of the implant to the needs of the host bone. This meant, that the implant had to be sufficiently rigid in the first period after surgical fixation of the fracture in order to enable primary bony union. Then, after approximately 6 weeks, the rigidity of the implant had to subsequently decrease to allow interfragmentary movement and thus stimulate the proliferation of external callus. Prior to the design studies for such an implant with adaptable mechanical properties, a thorough literature research was conducted with the aim to select suitable materials as well as technical and geometric features. Within this survey it was found that basically only implants made from biodegradable polymers such as Poly (L-lactide) (PLLA) possess the capability to mechanically degrade by means of hydrolytic resorption. However, these materials only provide moderate mechanical properties and hence are not suitable for application in load bearing implants. Further problems still associated with biodegradable polymers are the limited processability and the virtual uncontrollable propagation of degradation which is likely to lead to an early failure of such implants. In contrast, fibre-reinforced composite implants can easily be adjusted within a wide range to the stiffness of the host bone and also provide excellent fatigue behaviour depending on the fibre/matrix system employed. For this reason, it was decided to combine the advantageous features of both by integrating a resorbable polymer block into a non-degradable fibre reinforced implant body. The limiting criterion for the selection of a suitable thermoplastic composite material was, that both fibre and matrix had to be qualified for implantation into human bodies. In view of this demand and the mechanical loading conditions that are normally imposed on such implants carbon fibre reinforced Poly (ether ether ketone) (CF/PEEK) was found to be the most appropriate choice.

Additional aspects that decisively influenced the design of the implant are briefly listed below:

- easy surgical handling,
- geometric conformity with comparable stainless steel and titanium alloy implants,

- sufficient clearance between implant and bone at the fracture for unhampered proliferation of external callus,
- geometric adaptability of the implant to the contour of the host bone,
- no exposure of fibres in the surface of the implant to prevent undesirable foreign body reactions (the reinforcements have to be fully coated by matrix material), and
- good tribological properties (wear debris can lead to inflammatory body reactions).

Figure 1: Isometric view of the adaptable implant

Under consideration of the demands and boundary conditions imposed on the adaptable implant from the medical, mechanical and structural point of view the following design was developed. As can be seen in Figure 1, the implant consists of three separate components; tissue facing plate, degradable block and bone facing plate. The reasons that led to this design are manifold. Preliminary experiments on injection moulding PLLA into CF/PEEK blocks with incorporated grooves showed that only poor interfacial bonding between the two polymers was achieved by virtue of the PLLA's severe shrinkage upon solidification. It was therefore decided to mount the degradable block following the principle of positive connection. This way it was also ensured that only compressive loads induced by bending moments in primary load direction can be transferred through the insert. In order to allow sufficient room for proliferation of external callus beneath the plate, a clearance of approximately 5 mm between implant and bone was allowed in the middle section. The countersunk holes were designed similar to that of titanium LC-DCP plates (Limited Contact-Dynamic Compression Plate) in order to account for dynamic compression fixation (rotation and translation of screws). The principle of limited contact was incorporated by restricting the contact area to that of the bone facing plate. This way it was also ensured that both plates can be firmly assembled.

Regarding the manufacturing of the implant, the tissue facing plate had to be made from either short or knitted fibre-reinforced PEEK due to its complex shape. Since the latter is still not commercially available short fibre-reinforced PEEK (30vol.%) was chosen for calculations and manufacture of injection moulded prototypes. The bone facing plate was made from continuous fibre-reinforced PEEK since it has to carry most of the load and the

geometry was fairly simple. The biodegradable insert was also injection moulded in order to allow for compensation of the materials processing related shrinkage through mould design.

The achievable decrease in flexural rigidity was determined by varying the dimensions of the inserted block and the tissue facing plate. The dimensions of the beams in the central section of the bone facing plate were kept constant at 2 mm for stability reasons. The maximum width of both plates was set to 17 mm which is comparable with conventional femoral implants. Dependent on the initial rigidity the maximum achievable decrease was found to be in the order of 20%. With increasing thickness of the tissue facing plate the drop in rigidity gradually declined to 13%, however, the initial rigidity then reached values in excess of 40 Nm². Naturally, such an implant would be far to rigid. According to studies by Tayton *et. al*, who implanted a series of femoral implants with different flexural rigidities into humans, values in the order of 5-10 Nm² were found to be most appropriate for good bony union and proliferation of external callus [10].

PRELIMINARY TESTS

In the preliminary testing phase mainly three different aspects were of particular interest. First, it had to be clarified if the calculated drops in flexural rigidity could be validated in an actual experiment. In addition, the degradation behaviour of the PLLA blocks had to be characterised in order to estimate the rate at which the implant's rigidity would decline.

In order to determine the rate at which the flexural rigidity of the implant decreases, four-point-bending experiments were conducted following the method of Bradley *et al*. [11]. According to his studies a femoral implant should possess an initial flexural rigidity in the order of 2Nm/° deflection. Experiments on humans showed that softer plates led to acute pain and infections in the fracture. Using simplified prototypes with manually fitted PLLA blocks, four-point-bending tests were conducted with inserted and removed degradable blocks. This way, with an initial rigidity of 2.2Nm/° deflection, a drop of 5% was measured. Naturally, for the final implant prototype this would be not satisfactory, however, it was demonstrated that even with a manually fitted block a measurable rigidity drop could be achieved.

In the next step, the degradation behaviour of the PLLA material was taken under closer investigation. Storing specimens in blood substitute solution (Ringer solution) at 37°C the Young's modulus and tensile strength were measured after predefined dwell times. It was found that after 23 weeks the modulus and tensile strength had decreased from 3.7GPa and 50MPa to 2.9GPa and 43MPa respectively. This corresponded with a drop of 20% in modulus and 14% in strength. Under dynamic loading conditions the mechanical degradation progressed at a higher rate. Exposing the PLLA specimens to cyclic tensile loads at a frequency of 15Hz, and a total of 500.000 cycles the following results were obtained. With an initial dynamic modulus of roughly 1.45GPa, which corresponded with a static modulus of 3.7GPa, increasing the maximum tensile stress resulted in higher mechanical degradation rates (Figure 2). After 500.000 cycles at 37°C in Ringer solution and a maximum tensile stress of 16MPa the specimen had lost 12.8% of its dynamic modulus. The total duration of one experiment was 18.5 hours, meaning that no appreciable hydrolytic degradation had taken place. For comparison, experiments under dry conditions and in water at ambient temperature were conducted. It was found that the elevated temperature of 37°C and the simple presence of a liquid were mainly influencing the material's mechanical degradation. Being implanted into a human however, hydrolytic degradation, which is solely dependent on the dwell time,

and mechanical degradation will act simultaneously and thus enhance the mechanical degradation rate of the PLLA. This means, that the total decrease in modulus and strength will probably well exceed that measured under load free exposure as discussed earlier. How this behaviour is then going to effect the total drop in flexural rigidity of the implant is currently under investigation.

Figure 2: Normalised dynamic modulus of PLLA under cyclic loading

Another interesting effect that was observed during the dynamic testing of PLLA is its pronounced tendency to creep when exposed to Ringer solution at 37°C. Figure 3 shows the mean plastic deformation of the specimen tested under cyclic loading. It is evident that with increasing load the total deformation of the specimen also increases. However, even more significant is the fact that at ambient temperature, regardless of the surrounding medium, only marginal strain rates were measured (0.5-0.7%). This basically supports the conclusion made earlier that the temperature decisively influences the material's mechanical behaviour. Additional static tests, where a dead weight was used to apply a constant tensile stress showed similar results. Again, the specimen were put into tubs with Ringer solution at 37°C. With stresses of 3.5 and 5.5MPa mean plastic strains of 5.1 and 6.5% were measured after only 72 hours. Another 72 hours later the average strain amounted to 5.5 and 7.5%. For all specimen the transition from elastic to plastic deformation was reached after 2 hours at approximately 1.9% strain.

Figure 3: Mean plastic deformation of cyclic loaded PLLA specimens

Putting the results together it was concluded that the basically very brittle PLLA becomes ductile when being exposed to elevated temperatures and a liquid, in this case 37°C with water or Ringer solution. When external loads are applied mechanical degradation progresses long before hydrolytic degradation commences. However, it has to be taken into consideration that the dynamic tests had to be conducted at a frequency of 15Hz due to limitations in the testing equipment. Within the human body only frequencies of up to 5Hz do occur, meaning that the realistic situation could not be simulated. In the real situation the mechanical degradation would probably progress at a much slower rate. In order to better approximate this situation a new testing device is currently developed for dynamic four-point-bending implant prototypes with integrated PLLA blocks.

PRODUCTION OF PROTOTYPES

Prior to the production of prototypes it had to be decided on what manufacturing technique was most suited for producing the individual components of the implant. In order to satisfy the demand from the medical point of view concerning the surface finish and the coating of the reinforcements, only techniques that did not require any mechanical post-processing such as drilling or milling were taken into consideration. For the production of the continuous fibre-reinforced CF/PEEK bone facing plates, therefore, the near-net-shape technique was chosen. Figure 4 shows a photograph of the partly assembled mould. The inserts in the bottom half of the cavity, that form the countersunk holes and the gap for the biodegradable block, were removable in order to ease demoulding. For production of a part, pre-cut prepreg layers were filled into the bottom half of the mould. The assembled mould was then placed into a hot press where the material was heated to processing temperature, 420°C, at low external pressure. Once the melting temperature was reached the external pressure was increased to about 3MPa to ensure void-free consolidation.

Figure 4: Photograph of near-net-shape mould for the bone facing plate of the implant

Figure 5: Photograph of implant prototype

The tissue facing plate of the implant was produced employing a similar tool to that shown in Figure 4. The degradable insert made from PLLA was injection moulded and later inserted into the bone facing plate. In order to make sure that it was tightly fitted into the gap of the bottom plate it was cooled down to -40°C prior to assembly.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

A new composite osteosynthesis implant was designed and manufactured. It consists of three individual parts, two of which are made from CF/PEEK and the third from Poly (L-lactide). The purpose of this composition was to create a property profile that subsequently allows interfragmentary movement which, according to the latest medical findings, leads to better reconsolidation of fractures bones. The main advantage of this solution in comparison with the very rigid stainless steel and titanium alloy plates is, that the implant's mechanical properties can be tailored to the patients needs. By selecting tissue and bone facing plate and the degradable block from a kit system initial and remaining stiffness of the plate can be adjusted. All components were made employing injection moulding and near-net-shape forming in order to avoid post-processing steps. This way it was ensured that the reinforcing fibres were fully coated by matrix which was required from the medical side in view of possible inflammatory reactions. Preliminary tests on simplified prototypes showed that a reduction in flexural rigidity is possible by integrating a biodegradable block into the body of the implant. According to the calculations the maximum achievable drop should be in the order of 20%. This estimation is currently validated by means of four-point-bending tests on fully detailed implant prototypes. Poly (L-lactide) was found to be rather brittle and room temperature, however, when being exposed to a liquid at 37°C its properties change drastically. Dynamic tests in Ringer solution showed that mechanical degradation occurs long before hydrolytic degradation commences. In addition it also shows a pronounced tendency to creep under those conditions. If the PLLA is best suited for reducing the implants flexural rigidity is currently under investigation.

For the final testing phase which could possibly be *in-vivo* a microelectronic testing device, which is currently designed, will be build into the body of the implant. This way, the acting bending moments, the actual temperature at the fracture site, and possible slip between implant and screws will be monitored and sent to a nearby computer via telemetry. With the data, early determination of irregularities, such as loosening of the plate or inflammatory reactions in the fracture will be enabled, allowing a more precise assessment of the actual state of bony union and restoration of mechanical and structural strength.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the „Stiftung Rheinland-Pfalz für Innovation“ for its financial support (Project No. 8036-38 62 61 61/173c) and Boehringer-Ingelheim for the free material supply. In addition, thanks are also due to M. Huisman, F. Maier, T. Pfaff, V. Kessler, H. Weber, R. Krebs, M. Barth, J. Alsfasser and A. Starck for their valuable contribution to the presented work. Professor Friedrich gratefully acknowledges the FONDS DER CHEMISCHEN INDUSTRIE; Frankfurt, for support of his personal research activities in 1997.

REFERENCES

1. Kwarteng, K.B., Stark, C., "Carbon Fibre Reinforced PEEK (APC-2/AS-4) Composites for Orthopaedic Implants", *Sampe Quarterly*, Vol. 22, No. 1, 1990, pp. 10-14.

2. Schenk, R., Müller, J., Willenberg, H., "Experimentell-histologischer Beitrag zur Entstehung und Behandlung von Pseudoarthrosen", Hefte zur Unfallheilkunde, Vol. 94, 1986, pp. 15-24.
3. Aro, H.T., Kelly, P.J., Lewallen, D.G., Chao, E.Y.S., "The Effects of Physiologic Dynamic Compression on Bone Healing under External Fixation", Clin. Orthop. Rel. Res. Vol. 256, 1990, pp. 260-273.
4. Claes, L.E., Wilke, H.-J., Augat, P., Rübenacker, S., Margevicius, K.J., "Effect of Dynamization on Gap Healing of Diaphyseal Fractures under External Fixation", Clinical Biomechanics, Vol. 10, No. 5, 1995, pp. 227-234.
5. Claes, L.E., "Knochenheilung unter dynamischer Frakturstabilisierung, *Die Plattenosteosynthese und ihre Konkurrenzverfahren*, Wolter and Zimmermann, Ed., Springer Verlag, Berlin, 1991, pp. 61-65.
6. Goodship, A.E., Kenwright, J., "The Influence of Induced Micromovement upon the Healing of Experimental Tibial Fractures", Bone and Joint Surgery (B), Vol. 67 B, 1985, pp. 650-655.
7. Wu, J.J., Shyr, H.S., Chao, E.Y.S., Kelly, P.J., "Comparison of Osteotomy Healing under External Fixation Devices with Different Stiffness Characteristics", Bone and Joint Surgery (Am), Vol. 66 A, 1984, 1248-1286
8. Hunt, M.S., "Development of Carbon Fibre/Polysulfone Orthopaedic Implants", Materials & Design, Vol. 8, No. 2, 1987, pp. 113-119.
9. Tayton, K., Jonson-Nurse, C., McKibbin, B., Bradley, J., Hastings, G., "The Use of Semi-Rigid Plastic Plates for Fixation of Human Fractures", Bone and Joint Surgery, Vol. 64-B, No. 1, 1982, pp. 105-111.
10. Tayton, K., Bradley, J., "How Stiff should Semi-Rigid Fixation of the Human Tibia be?", Bone and Joint Surgery, Vol. 65-B, No. 3, 1983, pp. 312-315.
11. Bradley, J.S., Hastings, G.W., Johnson-Nurse, C., "Carbon Fibre Epoxy as High Strength, Low Modulus Material for Internal Fixation Plates, Biomaterials, Vol. 1, 1980, pp 38-40